

1 **Title: Proteomic validation of MEG-01-Derived Extracellular Vesicles as**
2 **Representative Models for Megakaryocyte- and Platelet-Derived**
3 **Extracellular Vesicles.**

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60 **Abstract (200 words):**

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62 Platelets and their extracellular vesicles (EVs) have emerged as promising liquid
63 biopsy biosources for cancer detection and monitoring. The megakaryoblastic
64 MEG-01 cell line offers a controlled system for generating platelet-like particles
65 (PLPs) and EVs through valproic acid induced differentiation. Here, we performed
66 comprehensive characterization and proteomic validation of MEG-01-derived
67 populations, native human platelets and their EVs using nanoparticle tracking
68 analysis, transmission electron microscopy, imaging flow cytometry and
69 quantitative proteomics.

70 MEG-01 megakaryocytic differentiation is characterized by polylobulated nuclei,
71 proplatelet formation and elevated CD41/CD42a expression. PLPs
72 predominantly exhibit an activated-like phenotype (CD62P+, degranulated
73 morphology), while microvesicles (100-500 nm) and exosomes (50-250 nm)
74 displayed size distributions and phenotypic markers consistent with native
75 platelet-derived EVs. Proteomics identified substantial core proteomes shared
76 across fractions and fraction-specific patterns consistent with selective cargo
77 partitioning during EV biogenesis.

78 **Functional enrichment indicated that MEG-01-derived vesicles preserve key**
79 **hemostatic, cytoskeletal, and immune pathways commonly associated with**
80 **platelet EV biology. Ingenuity Pathway Analysis showed that PLPs exhibit**
81 **proliferative transcriptional programs (elevated MYC/RB1/TEAD1, reduced**
82 **GATA1), while plasma exosomes display minimal differential pathway activation**
83 **compared to MEG-01 exosomes. Overall, these findings suggest that MEG-01-**
84 **derived EVs approximate certain aspects of megakaryocyte-lineage exosomes**
85 **and activated platelet-like states, although they do not fully replicate native**
86 **platelet biology. Notably, plasma exosomes show strong proteomic convergence**
87 **with MEG-01 exosomes, whereas platelet exosomes retain distinct activation-**
88 **related features.**

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92 **Keywords:** MEG-01 cell line, Extracellular Vesicles (EVs), Platelets, Proteomics,
93 Microvesicles (MVs), Exosomes (EXOs).

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98 **Introduction**

99 Contemporary biomedical research increasingly focuses on liquid biopsy as a
100 minimally invasive and highly informative source for the diagnosis and monitoring
101 of complex diseases, including cancer and inflammatory pathologies[1]. Within
102 this context, platelets and their derivatives, particularly extracellular vesicles
103 (EVs), including microvesicles (MVs) and exosomes (EXOs), have emerged as
104 bio-sources of critical importance[2].

105 Platelets are not merely effectors of hemostasis; they are dynamic cells that also
106 modulate immune response and tumor progression. Their highly conserved
107 molecular cargo, encapsulated within EVs, reflects the physiological state of their
108 parent cell (the megakaryocyte) and is modified following interaction with the
109 pathological microenvironment (e.g., tumor-educated platelets, TEPs)[3,4]. The
110 capacity of platelet EVs to transfer their protein, lipid, and nucleic acid cargo to
111 target cells positions them as key vehicles in intercellular communication and as
112 accessible reservoirs for the development of liquid biopsies [5,6].

113 Despite their promise, reliance on platelets and EVs derived from healthy donors
114 introduces a significant methodological challenge: the intrinsic heterogeneity of
115 the sample. Factors such as donor health status, blood processing, and genetic
116 variability contribute to the inconsistency of molecular profiles in EVs, hindering
117 standardization and reproducibility in large-scale functional and biomarker
118 analyses[7,8]. This variability underscores the need for *in vitro* cellular models
119 that enable the controlled and scalable production of EVs with a representative
120 molecular and biological composition.

121 The *in vitro* production of megakaryocytes and functional platelets relies primarily
122 on two human stem cell sources, each presenting a distinct balance of
123 advantages and methodological hurdles[9,10]. First, Human CD34+
124 hematopoietic stem cells (HSCs) isolated from diverse sources such as bone
125 marrow, peripheral blood, or cord blood can be efficiently differentiated into
126 mature megakaryocytes and platelets using both *in vivo* and *in vitro* approaches,
127 with protocols ranging from cytokine-driven culture systems to advanced 3D co-
128 culture methods that mimic the bone marrow microenvironment[11,12]. Second,
129 approaches utilizing human Pluripotent Stem Cells (hPSCs) have successfully

130 employed forward programming with transcription factors (e.g., GATA1, FLI1,
131 GATA2, and TAL1) to enable scalable production of mature megakaryocytes and
132 platelets[13–15] or the generation of immortalized progenitor cell lines yielding
133 functional platelets[16,17].

134 Despite these advancements, the field faces significant challenges that limit the
135 utility and scalability of stem cell-derived products. Key hurdles include the
136 complexity and lack of standardization across differentiation protocols, resulting
137 in high costs and low production efficiency. Furthermore, these systems are
138 constrained by the need for precise transcription factor manipulation and the often
139 limited quantitative evidence provided to ensure the functional equivalence of the
140 resulting platelets to those derived *in vivo*.

141 In this context, the MEG-01 cell line, an immortalized human megakaryoblastic
142 line, presents itself as a tractable and convenient alternative. Culturing MEG-01
143 cells provides a robust, scalable, and economical production system, capable of
144 releasing platelet-like particles (PLPs) and EVs under strictly controlled culture
145 conditions. Despite its demonstrated utility in preliminary functional studies, its
146 immortalized nature raises the critical question of whether MEG-01-derived EVs
147 (MEG-01 EVs) are molecularly and biologically equivalent to their counterparts
148 derived from primary human megakaryocytes and platelets.

149 The main objective of this study was to assess the extent to which MEG-01 cell
150 line-derived EVs recapitulate key molecular features of megakaryocyte- and
151 platelet-derived EVs. To address this, we performed a comprehensive
152 comparative proteomic analysis of MEG-01 EVs and EVs isolated from primary
153 platelets. Our results reveal substantial concordance in core signaling pathways
154 and functional markers, supporting the use of MEG-01-derived EVs as a
155 standardized and scalable surrogate model for selected aspects of platelet EV
156 biology, while acknowledging that they do not fully replicate native platelet
157 properties.

158 **Materials and Methods**

159 **Cell lines and culture conditions**

160 MEG-01 is a megakaryoblastic cell line that serves as an *in vitro* precursor of
161 PLPs[18]. The MEG-01 cell line was cultured in RPMI 1640 medium (BioWest,
162 Nuaille, France) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 1%
163 penicillin-streptomycin (P/S) (Biowest). Human embryonic kidney (HEK293T)
164 cells were grown in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) (Biowest)
165 supplemented with 10% FBS, without antibiotics. Both cell lines were obtained
166 from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, Manassas, VA), maintained
167 at 37°C in a humidified 5% CO₂ atmosphere, and used during their exponential
168 growth phase. Periodically mycoplasma testing and short tandem repeat (STR)
169 DNA profiling were performed to confirm cell line authenticity and prevent cross-
170 contamination or phenotypic drift. Human platelets from healthy donors served
171 as controls in selected experiments.

172 For EV isolation experiments, RPMI 1640 medium was supplemented with
173 exosome-depleted FBS (EXOD-FBS), prepared by ultracentrifugation at 100,000
174 × g for 18 h at 4°C under vacuum (Beckman Coulter Optima XL, 70 Ti rotor, Nyon,
175 Switzerland) followed by double filtration through 0.22 µm PVDF membrane
176 (MILLEX®VV Durapore®, Merck Millipore, Darmstadt, Germany) to eliminate
177 residual EVs and prevent contamination. **This procedure eliminated 70.93% of**
178 **the total extracellular vesicles present in FBS, as quantified by nanoparticle**
179 **tracking analysis and consistent with previous findings[19].**

180 **Reagents:**

181 2 mM Valproic acid (VPA), a histone deacetylases (HDAC) previously reported
182 to induce megakaryocytic differentiation and stimulate PLP production in MEG-
183 01 cells, was used in this study[20]. A 0.3 M VPA stock solution was prepared in
184 Milli-Q water and stored at -20°C. Prostaglandin E1 (PGE1) was dissolved in 2.82
185 mL DMSO to yield a 1,000 µM solution. Tyrode's buffer consisted of 134 mM
186 NaCl, 12 mM NaHCO₃, 2.9 mM KCl, 0.34 mM Na₂HPO₄, 1 mM MgCl₂, and 10
187 mM HEPES (pH 7.4). The 100x activation buffer contained 100 mM CaCl₂, 20

188 U/mL thrombin, and 1 mg/mL collagen. All these reagents were acquired from
189 Sigma-Aldrich/Merck (St. Louis, MO, USA).

190 **Lentiviral vector preparation, transduction of MEG-01 cell line and cell**
191 **sorting.**

192 Lentiviral vectors were generated by transient co-transfection of HEK293T cells
193 with a three-plasmid system: pHR'SINcppt-SE (carrying a GFP reporter gene), a
194 VSV.G envelope plasmid and psPAX2 packaging plasmid, using LipoD293™
195 (SignaGen Laboratories, Frederick, MD, USA). For transduction, 1 mL of high-
196 titer virus was added to 5 mL of MEG-01 cells in a T-25 flask. After 24 hours, cells
197 were centrifuged and the medium was replaced with fresh RPMI 1640 containing
198 antibiotics. Transduced cells were collected after 48 hours, and GFP⁺ cells were
199 sorted using a FACS Aria™ cytometer (BD Biosciences, Franklin Lakes, NJ,
200 USA). These transduced cells will hereafter be referred to as MEG-01 GFP⁺.

201 **MEG-01 Differentiation Protocol**

202 MEG-01 or MEG-01 GFP⁺ cells were differentiated into megakaryocytes using 2
203 mM VPA. Control MEG-01 GFP⁺ cells were cultured at 10⁵ cells/mL in T-75 flasks
204 with 15 mL EXOD-RPMI for 21 days, with partial medium replacement every 4
205 days to prevent oversaturation. VPA-treated MEG-01 or MEG-01 GFP⁺ cells
206 were cultured under identical conditions with 2 mM VPA added, and the medium
207 was refreshed every 4 days, adjusting VPA final concentration at 2 mM. Cell
208 populations were monitored throughout differentiation, and images were captured
209 using an EVOS Fluorescence Microscope (Advance Microscopy Group (AMG),
210 Life Technologies, Seattle, WA, USA).

211 **Cell, platelets and Extracellular Vesicle Isolation**

212 MEG-01 or MEG-01 GFP⁺ cells and their derived populations were isolated by
213 differential centrifugation. Cells were pelleted at 180 × g for 10 min at 4°C, and
214 the supernatant was filtered through a 5 μm membrane. PLPs were collected at
215 1,500 × g for 15 min, MVs at 10,000 × g for 40 min, and EXOs at 100,000 × g for
216 120 min using a Beckman Coulter Optima XL ultracentrifuge equipped with a 70
217 Ti fixed-angle rotor.

218 In accordance with MISEV guidelines[20], the terms MVs and EXOs in this study
219 designate operationally defined EV subtypes based on size, biogenesis, and
220 isolation method. The vesicles isolated at 10,000 x g for 40 min are classified as
221 large EVs (IEVs), traditionally known as MVs, typically ranging from 100-1000 nm
222 in diameter, enriched in canonical markers of megakaryocytic origin (e.g.,
223 CD41/CD42a), display externalized phosphatidylserine (PS) reflecting their
224 plasma membrane budding origin, and lack internal DNA. In contrast, vesicles
225 collected at 100,000 x g for 120 min fall in the 50-250 nm range, correspond to
226 small EVs (sEVs, commonly called EXOs), and exhibited both megakaryocytic
227 (CD41 and CD42a) and sEVs/EXO-associated (CD63) markers, consistent with
228 their endosomal biogenesis.

229 MEG-01 GFP+ cells were employed for size characterization and visualization by
230 imaging flow cytometry, while MEG-01 cells were used for proteomics assays to
231 minimize potential artifacts introduced by lentiviral transduction and GFP
232 overexpression[21].

233 Human platelet-rich plasma (PRP) was obtained from four healthy donors (n = 4).
234 Individual samples were pooled to minimize inter-donor variability. The pooled
235 blood was processed by centrifugation at 200 × g for 20 min (no brake,
236 acceleration set to 1), mixed with HEPES buffer containing 1 μM PGE1 to prevent
237 activation, and pelleted at 800 × g for 20 min (no brake, acceleration set to 1).
238 Platelets were resuspended in Tyrode's buffer, split into control and activated
239 groups. Platelet activation was carried out at 37 °C incubating with activation
240 buffer (final concentration 1X) for 1 hour. Platelet-derived EVs were isolated using
241 the previously described differential centrifugation protocol.

242 **Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM).**

243 TEM was employed to investigate the size and ultrastructure of VPA-
244 differentiated MEG-01 GFP+ cells, their derived PLPs and EVs, as well as human
245 platelets and their corresponding EVs. Samples were fixed in 2.5%
246 glutaraldehyde and 2% paraformaldehyde (0.05 M cacodylate buffer, pH 7.4,
247 4°C, 24 h), washed in 0.1 M cacodylate buffer, and post-fixed with 1% osmium

248 tetroxide. They were sequentially stained with 1% tannic acid and 1% uranyl
249 acetate, embedded in EMBED 812, and sectioned (50–70 nm) using a LEICA S
250 ultramicrotome (Leica Microsystems, Wetzlar, Germany). Sections were
251 counterstained with uranyl acetate and lead citrate before imaging. EVs were
252 negatively stained with 1% uranyl acetate on carbon-coated grids (CF 300 Cu)
253 for 5 min, stained for 1 min, and air-dried. Imaging was performed using a ZEISS
254 Libra 120 plus TEM (120 kV, LaB₆ filament) (Carl Zeiss Microscopy, Oberkochen,
255 Germany).

256 **Flow cytometry analysis.**

257 MEG-01 GFP⁺ cells and PLPs isolated from the VPA differentiation protocol were
258 analyzed by flow cytometry. Cells were isolated and washed with PBS,
259 centrifuged at 180 x g for 10 min for cells and 1500 x g for 15 min for PLPs, and
260 incubated in the dark for 30 min with anti-CD41-PE (Invitrogen, ThermoFisher
261 Scientific, Maltham, MA, USA) and anti-CD42a-APC (Miltenyi Biotec, Bergisch
262 Gladbach, Germany) antibodies, diluted as recommended by the manufacturer.
263 After washing, cells were resuspended in 100 µl PBS and analyzed with the
264 FACS Canto II flow cytometer (BD Bioscience) using DIVA software (BD
265 Bioscience). PLPs and platelet activation status was assessed using CD41-PE,
266 CD42a-APC, and CD62P-BV421 (BD Bioscience) antibodies, with samples
267 resuspended in PBS-EDTA (2 mM) post-washing, in the FACS Canto II flow
268 cytometer (BD Bioscience).

269 **ImageStream Analysis**

270 MEG-01 GFP⁺ cells from the 21-day VPA protocol were isolated by centrifugation
271 (180 x g for 10 min). Cells were stained with anti-CD41-PE and anti-CD42a-APC,
272 incubated for 15 min in the dark, fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde, permeabilized
273 with 0.1% Triton X-100, and stained with Hoechst for 3 min. Platelets and PLPs
274 were centrifuged at 800 or 1500 x g for 15 min, were stained with anti-CD41-PE,
275 anti-CD42a-APC and the CD62P activation marker, incubated for 15 min and
276 resuspended in PBS-EDTA buffer (2 mM). MVs were obtained by centrifugation
277 at 10,000 x g for 40 min, stained with anti-CD41-PE, anti-CD42a-APC, 7AAD
278 DNA marker, and Annexin V (Annexin V-CF Blue 7-AAD Kit (Abcam, Cambridge,

279 UK), and resuspended in Annexin buffer. EXOs were obtained by
280 ultracentrifugation (100,000 x g for 2 h) and stained with anti-CD41-PE, anti-
281 CD42a-APC, and anti-CD63-PE-Cy7 (BD Pharmingen, BD Bioscience),
282 incubated for 40 min, and resuspended in PBS. Data were acquired using the
283 ImageStream Mark II cytometer (Amnis, Seattle, WA, USA) and analyzed with
284 IDEAS software (Amnis).

285 **Nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA).**

286 EV pellets (MVs at 10,000 x g; EXO at 100,000 x g) from MEG-01 GFP+ cells,
287 platelets, and plasma were resuspended in 1 mL sterile PBS (pH 7.4).
288 Measurements were performed using a Malvern NanoSight NS300 equipped with
289 a 405 nm laser, sCMOS camera, and NTA software version 2.3 (Malvern
290 Panalytical, Malvern, UK). Instrument performance was verified using 100 nm
291 silica microspheres. Samples were diluted to the optimal detection range and
292 injected at 50 μ L/min at 25°C. Five 10-second videos were recorded with different
293 camera settings (CL=8 and DT=15 for MVs, CL=10 and DT=15 for EXOs), and
294 size distribution and concentration were averaged using GraphPad Prism™
295 software (version 9.4.1 for Windows, La Joya, CA, USA). **NTA measurements**
296 **were performed on three biological replicates (independent EV preparations) with**
297 **five technical replicates per sample, defined as five consecutive 60-second video**
298 **recordings of the same aliquot to account for instrument variability.**

299 **Zeta Potential and electrophoretic mobility of Extracellular Vesicles (EVs).**

300 Electrophoretic mobility (μ e) and Zeta Potential (ZP) of the EV fractions were
301 measured using a Malvern Zetasizer® NanoZeta ZS (Malvern Panalytical).
302 Fractions were resuspended in phosphate buffer (pH 7.4, 1.13 mM NaH₂PO₄) to
303 prevent electrode damage and analyzed at 25°C.

304 **Protein extraction, digestion and peptide clean-up**

305 EVs from plasma, platelets, and MEG-01 cultures were lysed in 4.5% SDS and
306 0.1 M Tris-HCl (pH 8.5) with 5 mM tris(2-carboxyethyl)phosphine (TCEP) and 10
307 mM chloroacetamide (CAA). All samples were boiled at 95°C for 10 minutes,

308 sonicated for 10 minutes and centrifugated to remove cellular debris. Protein
309 concentration was determined using the Pierce BCA Protein Assay Kit (Thermo
310 Fisher Scientific). Aliquots of 40 µg protein were digested using the single-pot,
311 solid-phase (SP3) sample preparation method[22] with 100 µg/µL carboxylate-
312 modified magnetic beads (GE Healthcare, Chicago, IL, USA) at a 10:1
313 bead:protein ratio (w/w). SDS was removed by washing twice with 80% (v/v)
314 ethanol. Samples were acidified to pH 2-2.5 and desalted using an Oasis HLB
315 96-well µElution Plate (Waters, Milford, MA, USA) according to the
316 manufacturer's instructions. Peptides were resuspended in 0.5% formic acid and
317 2% acetonitrile, quantified by A280 measurements using NanoDrop (Thermo
318 Fisher Scientific), and stored at -20°C until Liquid Chromatography with tandem
319 Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) analysis. All samples were processed in
320 triplicate to ensure reproducibility and reliability of the results.

321 **LC-MS/MS analysis**

322 Purified tryptic digests (200 ng peptide load) were separated using the
323 predefined 15 SPD method (88-min gradient) on an Evosep One system
324 (Evosep, Denmark) coupled online to a timsTOF Flex mass spectrometer (Bruker
325 Daltonics, Germany). Peptides were delivered to a fused-silica emitter (20-µm ID;
326 Bruker, Germany) mounted in a CaptiveSpray nanoelectrospray source (Bruker).
327 The emitter was connected to a 15-cm × 150-µm reversed-phase analytical
328 column packed with 1.9-µm C18 particles (PepSep Fifteen, Bruker). The column
329 was maintained at 60 °C using a thermostated column oven (Bruker). Mobile
330 phases consisted of water (A) and acetonitrile (B), both containing 0.1% formic
331 acid (LC-MS grade, Fisher Scientific).

332 The ion mobility dimension was calibrated using three ions from the Agilent ESI-
333 L Tuning Mix (m/z, 1/K₀ values: 622.0289 Th, 0.9848 Vs cm⁻²; 922.0097 Th,
334 1.1895 Vs cm⁻²; 1221.9906 Th, 1.3820 Vs cm⁻²). Collision energy was linearly
335 reduced from 59 eV at 1/K₀ = 1.6 Vs cm⁻² to 20 eV at 1/K₀ = 0.6 Vs cm⁻².

336 All samples were acquired using a DIA-PASEF method under the long-gradient
337 configuration (m/z range: 400–1201 Th; 1/K₀ range: 0.6–1.6 Vs cm⁻²; 16 × 25 Th
338 diaPASEF windows).

339 **Proteomics Data analysis**

340 Proteomic analyses were performed using three biological replicates
341 (independent MEG-01 cultures and platelet samples) and five technical replicates
342 (duplicate LC-MS/MS runs of each digested sample) to account for biological
343 variability and instrument consistency. RAW MS data were processed using
344 Spectronaut v18.1 (Biognosys AG, Zurich, Switzerland) for DIA analysis,
345 searching a human proteome FASTA file (SwissProt, Geneva, Switzerland). All
346 data analyses and visualizations were performed using R language. Raw data
347 was initially normalized using the standard cyclic loess normalization process[23]
348 implemented at limma package[24]. Several unsupervised hierarchical clustering
349 analyses were performed and visualized as heatmaps using normalized and
350 standardized protein abundance values (z-scores). All proteins commonly
351 identified across the compared groups were included in the clustering, without
352 any filtering. Clusters were generated using the complete-linkage algorithm
353 based on Euclidean distances between samples[25]. Also, a dimensionality
354 reduction study was applied using both a linear method (Principal Component
355 Analysis, PCA) and a nonlinear method (t-distributed Stochastic Neighbor
356 Embedding, t-SNE) [26] to analyze group clusterizations. Gene Ontology
357 (GO)[27,28], Reactome[29], and Bioplanet[30] functional enrichments were
358 performed using Genecodis, a bioinformatics tool that integrates diverse
359 annotation sources[31]. Enrichment was conducted independently for the full set
360 of proteins identified in each group. Additional functional analyses were
361 generated through the use of IPA[32] and the Comparison analysis tool (QIAGEN
362 Inc., version 2024.1;[https://www.qiagenbioinformatics.com/products/ingenuity-](https://www.qiagenbioinformatics.com/products/ingenuity-pathway-analysis)
363 [pathway-analysis](https://www.qiagenbioinformatics.com/products/ingenuity-pathway-analysis)). IPA analysis was performed over differentially expressed
364 proteins obtained between each natural product (Platelets, MVs and EXOs) and
365 its corresponding MEG-01-derived populations. IPA provides activation z-scores
366 indicating a predicted level of activation/inhibition in upstream regulators or
367 canonical pathways.

368 **Statistical Analysis**

369 Data were analyzed using Microsoft® Excel® for Microsoft 365 MSO (64-bit,
370 v2409), GraphPad Prism 9.4.1 and FlowJo V10 software (Treestar, Ashland, OR,
371 USA). Values are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Differences
372 between groups were assessed using unpaired two-tailed t-tests, Holm-Šídák's
373 multiple unpaired t-test or one-at ANOVA. Furthermore, functional enrichment
374 from GeneCodis provides statistical significance by hypergeometric and
375 Wallenius tests corrected via Benjamini/Hochberg fold-discovery rate (FDR)[31].
376 An FDR-adjusted p-value < 0.01 was then considered for enrichment terms in
377 GeneCodis. Also, relative enrichment scores are provided measuring the
378 proportion between the number of proteins for a specific term divided by the size
379 of the input or the total number of proteins. **The differentially expressed proteins**
380 **included in the IPA analysis were selected using a logFC > 1 and an adjusted p-**
381 **value < 0.01 , based on the false-discovery rate correction (Benjamini–Hochberg**
382 **method) implemented in the *limma* R package [24].** Finally, IPA analysis for
383 functional pathways enrichment and upstream regulators prediction was
384 performed using **the Comparison** analysis tool that combines p-value (Fisher's
385 exact test, p-value < 0.05) for enrichment and a bespoke activation z-score for
386 directionality, allowing for direct, quantitative comparison of canonical pathway
387 activity or upstream regulators across two datasets and visualization as a
388 comparative heatmap (IPA, Qiagen Inc. version 2024.1).

389 **Results:**

390 ***Fluorescence-Based Model for Tracking Cellular and Extracellular Vesicle*** 391 ***Populations.***

392 To establish a reproducible *in vitro* model for studying megakaryocytic
393 differentiation and EV production, we transduced the MEG-01 cells with the
394 lentiviral vector pHR'SINcpt-SE, which constitutively expresses green
395 fluorescent protein (GFP). Flow cytometry confirmed a transduction efficiency of
396 $99.71 \pm 0.12\%$ (mean \pm SD, n=3) based on GFP expression compared to non-
397 transduced controls. This fluorescence-based system, termed MEG-01 GFP+,

398 enabled robust tracking of cellular populations (MEG-01 GFP+ cells, PLPs, MVs,
399 and EXOs) throughout subsequent experiments (Data not shown).

400 ***Characterization of Megakaryocytic differentiation in MEG-01 GFP+ cells.***

401 We employed a 21-day differentiation protocol using 2 mM VPA[20]. MEG-01
402 GFP+ cells subjected to treatment were replenished with fresh VPA-
403 supplemented culture medium every 4 days, while control cells were maintained
404 at appropriate confluence and nutrient levels, without VPA exposure. Throughout
405 the differentiation process, both culture images and TEM images were captured
406 to evaluate the morphological and phenotypic changes of the MEG-01 GFP+ cell
407 line (**Figure 1A and 1B**).

408 In the early stages of differentiation, most cells adhered to the flask surface,
409 transitioning from suspension to adherence, which is necessary for differentiation
410 initiation (**Figure 1A, panel 1**). By days 8–14, cells exhibited polylobed nuclei
411 indicative of endoreplication, along with cytoplasmic expansion and the formation
412 of membranous protrusions contributing to proplatelet development (**Figure 1A,**
413 **panels 2 and 3; Figure 1B, panel 1**). These protrusions progressively elongate
414 and branch, accumulating organelles and widening to form thick pseudopods
415 from which proplatelets emerge (**Figure 1A, panel 4; Figure 1B, panel 2**). This
416 process has been described as microtubule-driven in mature
417 megakaryocytes[33], although microtubules are not directly visualized in our
418 images. Proplatelet formation expands throughout the megakaryocyte cytoplasm
419 until full conversion into proplatelet masses, which are released from the cell
420 (**Figure 1A, panel 5**). Finally, the nucleus is expelled from the proplatelet mass,
421 and individual platelets are released from proplatelet tips into the culture medium,
422 generating PLPs.

423 In addition to morphological and phenotypic changes, flow cytometry analysis of
424 megakaryocytic specific markers CD41 and CD42a revealed significantly higher
425 expression in VPA-treated cells compared to controls throughout the
426 differentiation protocol. On day 12, VPA-treated cells expressed CD41 at 74.55
427 $\pm 13.89\%$ (vs. $26.83 \pm 5.70\%$ in controls, $p < 0.001$, $n=5$) and CD42a at $90.81 \pm$

428 2.17% (vs. $38.03 \pm 6.88\%$, $p < 0.001$, $n = 5$) (**Figure 1C**). Furthermore, imaging flow
429 cytometry confirmed peripheral localization of CD41 and CD42a at the plasma
430 membrane, ubiquitous GFP distribution, and polylobed nuclei stained with
431 Hoechst, validating endoreplication (**Figure 1D**).

432 Collectively, these results demonstrate that VPA induces megakaryocytic
433 differentiation with key morphological and immunophenotypic features.

434 ***Platelet-Like Particles from VPA-treated MEG-01 GFP+ Cells Mimic***
435 ***Activated Platelets.***

436 VPA-induced PLPs, were collected by centrifugation and compared to
437 physiological platelets using TEM, flow cytometry and imaging flow cytometry.
438 **Figure 2A** shows a comparative sequence of TEM images displaying the different
439 physiological stages of platelets and PLPs. Control platelets (Control PLTs) were
440 discoid and rounded ($2\text{-}3\ \mu\text{m}$ diameter), containing mitochondria and a well-
441 defined canalicular system for granule secretion (e.g., alpha and dense
442 granules). In contrast, activated platelets (Activated PLTs) were slightly smaller,
443 with “empty” cytoplasm post-granule release, predominantly filled with protein
444 and ribosomal material. Activated PLTs are tightly bound by fibrin-mediated
445 membrane interactions within the thrombi, exhibiting a “vacant” cytoplasm. PLPs
446 showed heterogeneity: most resembled activated PLTs in size ($3\text{-}5\ \mu\text{m}$) and
447 “empty” cytoplasm, while a smaller proportion resembled Control PLTs, with
448 canalicular systems, granules, and mitochondria ($4000\times$ magnification). TEM also
449 revealed fragmented MEG-01 GFP+ cells with nuclei pulled down during
450 centrifugation (**Figure 2A**).

451 Flow cytometry assessed CD41 and CD42a expression in PLPs every 4 days,
452 showing significantly elevated expression from VPA-treated cells compared to
453 controls (CD41: $81.15 \pm 21.73\%$ vs. $38.18 \pm 7.94\%$, $p < 0.05$, $n = 5$; CD42a: 69.11
454 $\pm 5.49\%$ vs. $29.41 \pm 8.66\%$, $p < 0.05$, $n = 5$), with stable levels by day 12 (**Figure**
455 **2B**). PLP activation was evaluated via CD62P (P-selectin) expression, present
456 only on activated PLT membrane. PLPs exhibited higher CD62P levels ($38.61 \pm$
457 13.57%) than Control PLTs ($6.49 \pm 0.53\%$, $p < 0.01$, $n = 3$) but lower than Activated

458 PLTs ($93.67 \pm 1.25\%$, $p < 0.0001$, $n=3$). The mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) of
459 CD62P was significantly higher in PLPs than in Control PLTs (212 ± 30.01 vs.
460 19.56 ± 2.24 ; $p < 0.05$, $n=3$), and, in turn, much higher in Activated PLTs ($1187 \pm$
461 197.1 ; $p < 0.0001$, $n=3$), showing a shift in the histogram plot (**Figure 2C**).

462 Imaging flow cytometry confirmed peripheral CD41 and CD42a localization at the
463 plasma membrane in PLPs and platelets, with homogeneous CD62P expression
464 in PLPs and activated PLTs, although higher intensity in activated PLTs, while it
465 was absent in Control PLTs (**Figure 2D**). Morphologically, Control PLTs
466 appeared spherical, Activated PLTs present membrane extensions, and PLPs
467 displayed heterogeneous patterns with larger size. GFP was present in PLPs,
468 whereas it is absent in physiological platelets, allowing tracking due to inheritance
469 from VPA-treated MEG-01 GFP+ cell. Based on peak CD41 and CD42a
470 expression, day 12 was selected to proceed with the study of the following
471 vesicular populations.

472 ***Characterization of Microvesicles (MVs) from VPA-treated MEG-01 GFP+*** 473 ***cells.***

474 MVs are a subtype of EVs formed through the outward budding of the plasma
475 membrane and typically range from 100 to 1,000 nm in diameter. MVs reflect the
476 molecular signature of their cell of origin and participate in physiological and
477 pathological processes[34]. In order to further characterize the MVs produced by
478 VPA-treated MEG-01 GFP+ cells (MVs MEG-01), these EVs were isolated and
479 subsequently compared to MVs from control platelets (MVs Control PLTs),
480 activated PLTs (MVs Activated PLTs), and plasma (MVs Plasma).

481 Using NTA, a technique that measures particle size and concentration in
482 suspension by analyzing their Brownian motion under laser illumination, we
483 determined that MVs MEG-01 ranged from 100–500 nm, with multimodal peaks
484 at 170, 242, and 354 nm (**Figure 3A**). MVs Control PLTs ranged from 100-400
485 nm with peaks at 110, 163, 244, and 351 nm (**Figure 3B**), while plasma-derived
486 MVs (MVs Plasma) were smaller (60-200 nm), with bimodal peaks at 64 and 165
487 nm (**Figure 3C**). Interestingly, MVs Activated PLTs exhibited a similar size
488 distribution to MVs MEG-01, ranging from 100-500 nm with multimodal peaks at

489 186, 325, and 470 nm (**Figures 3D**). TEM confirmed vesicle sizes and
490 morphological characteristics of different MVs populations (**Figures 3A-D**).

491 As previously indicated, NTA also allows precise quantification of particle
492 concentration. MVs Control PLTs had fewer particles/mL of blood than MVs
493 Activated PLTs ($1.853 \times 10^7 \pm 7.06 \times 10^6$ particles/mL of blood vs $7.29 \times 10^7 \pm$
494 1.47×10^7 particles/mL of blood; $p < 0.001$; $n = 3$) and also less concentration than
495 MVs Plasma ($1.383 \times 10^8 \pm 2.687 \times 10^7$ particles/mL of blood; $p < 0.0001$, $n = 3$),
496 the latter being the MV with highest concentration. MVs MEG-01 GFP+ exhibit
497 concentrations similar to MVs Control PLTs ($1.7136 \times 10^7 \pm 1.38 \times 10^7$
498 particles/mL of media, $n = 5$) (**Figure 3E**). MVs were also assessed by their zeta
499 potential, which measures the electrical potential between the vesicle membrane
500 and the surrounding solution. **Figure 3F** shows that all MVs isolated from the
501 different samples have negative potentials (-9.143 to -14.075 mV), ensuring
502 biological origin, suspension stability and preventing aggregation due to
503 electrostatic repulsion.

504 Phenotypic characterization by imaging flow cytometry assessed CD41, CD42a,
505 Annexin V (indicating phosphatidylserine exposure), and 7-AAD (for DNA
506 content). MVs MEG-01 expressed GFP, Annexin V and peripheral CD41 and
507 CD42a, without 7AAD labeling, confirming their megakaryocytic origin and
508 distinguishing them from apoptotic bodies (**Figure 3G**). MVs Control PLTs and
509 MVs Activated PLTs lacked GFP and 7AAD but expressed Annexin V, CD41 and
510 CD42a, while some MVs Plasma lacked CD41 and CD42a, suggesting diverse
511 cellular origins.

512 All together, these data indicate that MVs MEG-01 closely mimic MVs activated
513 PLT in size distribution and immunophenotype.

514 ***Characterization of Exosomes (EXOs) from VPA-treated MEG-01 GFP+***
515 ***cells.***

516 EXOs are small EVs typically ranging from 50 to 250 nm in diameter, which
517 originate from the endosomal pathway through the inward budding of
518 multivesicular bodies (MVBs). Their biogenesis is characterized by the selective

519 sorting of cargo via ESCRT (endosomal sorting complexes required for transport)
520 machinery distinguishing from MVs[34].

521 For a comprehensive analysis, EXOs were isolated by ultracentrifugation at
522 100,000 × g and subsequently compared among VPA-treated MEG-01 GFP+
523 cells (EXOs MEG-01), control platelets (EXOs Control PLTs), activated platelets
524 (EXOs Activated PLTs), and plasma (EXOs Plasma). NTA and TEM analyses
525 verified that EXOs ranged in size from 50 to 250 nm and exhibited characteristic
526 morphology. EXOs MEG-01 displayed a bimodal size distribution (peaks at 112
527 and 153 nm), resembling EXOs activated PLT (mode at 112 nm). EXOs Control
528 PLTs exhibit a multimodal distribution (peaks at 55, 107, 140, 193, and 244 nm),
529 while EXOs Plasma showed a bimodal distribution (54 and 144 nm) (**Figures 4A-**
530 **D**).

531 Activated platelets produced a significantly higher concentration of EXOs
532 Activated PLTs ($9.68 \times 10^7 \pm 9.16 \times 10^6$ particles/mL of blood) compared to EXOs
533 control PLTs ($4.083 \times 10^7 \pm 1.89 \times 10^7$ particles/mL of blood, $p < 0.01$, $n = 3$). EXOs
534 MEG-01 had a similar concentration to EXOs Control PLTs ($4.14 \times 10^7 \pm 1.697 \times$
535 10^6 particles/mL of media), whereas EXOs Plasma had a similar concentration to
536 EXOs Activated PLTs ($8.333 \times 10^7 \pm 1.646 \times 10^7$ particles/mL of blood) (**Figure**
537 **4E**). Zeta potential values ranged from -8.647 to -16.165 mV, indicating biological
538 origin, colloidal stability, and lipid-rich composition in all samples (**Figure 4F**).

539 Phenotypically characterization was performed using imaging flow cytometry,
540 assessing the expression of distinct markers (**Figure 4G**). In this case, CD63 was
541 analyzed as a distinctive marker of MVB biogenesis. EXOs MEG-01 expressed
542 GFP, CD41/CD42a, and CD63, confirming their megakaryocytic and exosomal
543 identity. EXOs Control PLTs and EXOs Activated PLTs similarly expressed
544 CD41, CD42a, and CD63, verifying platelet origin. In contrast, some EXOs
545 Plasma lacked CD41 and CD42a, suggesting biosynthesis from non-platelets or
546 megakaryocytic cell types (**Figure 4G**).

547 These results demonstrate that EXOs MEG-01 share size distributions and
548 CD41+/CD42a+/CD63+ profiles with platelet-derived EXOs.

549 ***Proteomics Reveals Distinct Signatures and Functional Specialization of***
550 ***MEG-01-Derived Vesicles.***

551 To comprehensively characterize the proteomic landscape of VPA-treated MEG-
552 01 cells (MEG-01) and their derivatives (PLPs, MVs MEG-01 and EXOs MEG-
553 01), we analyzed protein abundance profiles across multiple sample types using
554 quantitative LC-MS/MS. Unsupervised hierarchical clustering analysis revealed
555 clear compartment-specific expression patterns (**Figure 5A**). The heatmap
556 demonstrated coherent clustering within sample classes, with expression
557 gradients indicative of distinct proteomic signatures for each fraction type.
558 Complementary Venn diagrams illustrated the intersection of identified proteins
559 across the four main fractions, revealing substantial overlaps in core proteomes
560 while highlighting unique protein subsets specific to each compartment. These
561 findings suggest both shared biological functions and specialized cargo-sorting
562 mechanisms operate during PLP/EV biogenesis.

563 To elucidate the functional significance of these proteomic profiles, we performed
564 pathway enrichment analysis using GeneCodis. The top 10 most significant terms
565 with FDR-adjusted p-value < 0.01 were considered. Bioplanet pathway analysis
566 revealed strong enrichment of specific signaling modules within vesicle fractions
567 (**Figure 5B**). Pathways related to actin cytoskeleton organization and cell
568 migration (*PI3K subunit p85 role in regulation of actin organization and cell*
569 *migration*), Rho family regulation (*D4-GDI signaling pathway*) and receptor-
570 mediated signaling (*CBL-mediated ligand-induced downregulation of EGF*
571 *receptors*) showed particularly higher significance in MEG-01 cells, PLPs and
572 MVs MEG-01 compared to EXOs MEG-01. In contrast, protein biosynthesis
573 pathways were more prominent in EXOs MEG-01, showing the highest
574 enrichment scores in *Translation* and *Cytoplasmic ribosomal protein* categories.

575 Gene Ontology (GO) Biological Process analysis demonstrated that all fractions
576 were strongly enriched in pathways governing RNA and protein biosynthesis
577 (**Figure 5C**). Notably, enrichment scores for mRNA biosynthetic pathways
578 (*mRNA processing*, *RNA splicing* and *mRNA splicing via spliceosome*) were
579 highest in parent MEG-01 cells and progressively declined in derived vesicles,

580 suggesting dilution or functional specialization of this machinery during vesicle
581 formation. Ribosome biosynthesis pathways (*Ribosome biogenesis* and *rRNA*
582 *processing*) displayed elevated enrichment in MEG-01 cells and PLPs, whereas
583 protein intracellular trafficking pathways (*Protein transport* and *Intracellular*
584 *protein transport*) and *Mitochondrial translation* showed reduced significance in
585 EXOs MEG-01. Reactome analysis (**Supplementary Figure 1A**) corroborated
586 these findings, highlighting dominant overrepresentation of RNA metabolism and
587 translation pathways across all fractions.

588 Collectively, this functional profiling indicates a transition from a primary
589 biosynthetic role within MEG-01 cells to specialized functions in intercellular
590 communication and cell signaling within derived EVs.

591 To obtain a global perspective on the proteomic landscape of MEG-01 derivatives
592 relative to their natural counterparts, we performed unsupervised dimensionality
593 reduction techniques, including principal component analysis (PCA) and t-
594 distributed stochastic neighbor embedding (tSNE) on the complete dataset
595 (**Figure 5D**). PCA revealed clear separation of experimental groups, with the first
596 principal component accounted for 43.7% of the variance, clearly separating
597 MEG-01 cells, platelets, MVs and EXOs. The second principal component (18%)
598 allowed further sub-clustering confirming high intragroup consistency and distinct
599 molecular identities across groups. Notably, PLPs (cyan color) segregated more
600 closely with MEG-01 cells (pink color) than with native platelets regardless of
601 activation status. Independent t-SNE analysis confirmed these PCA results,
602 producing tight, well-separated clusters corresponding to each sample group and
603 experimental condition.

604 GO Cellular Component analysis revealed significant enrichment of *Cytoplasm*,
605 *Nucleoplasm* and *Mitochondrion* terms in PLPs, mirroring the profile observed in
606 parental MEG-01 cells. In contrast, MVs MEG-01 and EXOs MEG-01 exhibited
607 notable enrichment in *Extracellular exosome* and *Blood microparticle* terms,
608 respectively (**Supplementary Figure 1B**). These findings suggest that PLPs
609 retain substantial intracellular components, which may arise from arrested

610 maturation toward a terminally differentiated platelet phenotype or from
611 contamination with MEG-01-derived cellular debris during the isolation protocol.

612 ***Functional Proteomic Profiling Distinguishes PLPs from Native Platelets***
613 ***and MEG-01 cells.***

614 Hierarchical clustering of protein abundance z-scores demonstrated clear
615 segregation of native platelets (control and activated), PLPs and MEG-01 cells
616 into distinct groups (**Figure 6A**). Venn diagram analysis revealed a substantial
617 core proteome of 3,551 proteins shared across all samples, alongside fraction-
618 specific subsets comprising 492 proteins unique to PLPs and 688 to MEG-01
619 cells, indicating selective protein sorting during PLP biogenesis from MEG-01
620 precursors. Interestingly, platelet activation resulted in the detection of 69
621 proteins and the loss of 239 proteins compared to resting platelets (**Figure 6A**).

622 Functional enrichment analysis across multiple databases revealed convergent
623 proteomic signatures. BioPlanet pathway analysis identified significant
624 overrepresentation of cytoskeletal and signaling modules, together with platelet-
625 specific programs and metabolic pathways (**Figure 6B**). GO Biological Process
626 analysis corroborated these findings, demonstrating strong enrichment in protein
627 and vesicle trafficking, protein biosynthesis and cellular respiration (**Figure 6C**).
628 Reactome pathway analysis further confirmed dominant enrichment in protein
629 trafficking, immune-related programs and platelet-specific pathways
630 (**Supplementary Figure 2A**). These results indicates that PLP proteomes
631 appear closer to MEG-01 cells than platelets, likely influenced by residual debris
632 or incomplete maturation.

633 GO Cellular Component analysis localized the identified proteins predominantly
634 to *Extracellular exosome* and *Cytoplasm* compartments, with substantial
635 contributions of mitochondrial fraction (*Mitochondrion*) (**Supplementary Figure**
636 **2B**). Remarkably, nuclear proteins (*Nucleoplasm*) remained present in PLPs,
637 suggesting co-purification of cellular debris containing nuclear components from
638 MEG-01 cells during the isolation process.

639 ***Comparative Proteomics Identifies Conserved Hemostatic Programs in***
640 ***Platelet, Plasma, and MEG-01-Derived MVs.***

641 Proteomic analysis of MVs Control PLTs, MVs Activated PLTs, MVs Plasma, and
642 MVs MEG-01 demonstrated robust sample discrimination through hierarchical
643 clustering, while Venn analysis identified both shared and fraction-specific protein
644 signatures (**Figure 6D**). A substantial core proteome of 1,904 proteins was
645 present across all MVs sources, indicative of common vesicular biogenesis
646 mechanisms. However, significant differences emerged: MVs MEG-01 contained
647 2,846 unique proteins, reflecting their distinct cellular origin. MVs Plasma
648 exhibited 221 expressed proteins compared to platelets MVs, with 141 being
649 unique to this fraction. Interestingly, MVs Activated PLTs showed dramatic cargo
650 enrichment, gaining 761 proteins upon activation, 190 of which were exclusive to
651 this activated state.

652 Functional enrichment analysis revealed that MV proteomes were dominated by
653 hemostatic and signaling pathways across all sources. BioPlanet pathway
654 analysis emphasized cytoskeletal remodeling, platelet activation programs, and
655 stress/checkpoint responses (**Figure 6E**). GO Biological Process terms
656 concentrated on protein trafficking, protein biosynthesis and hemostatic functions
657 (**Figure 6F**). Reactome analysis reinforced these patterns through enrichment in
658 trafficking, hemostasis, and immune surveillance pathways (**Supplementary**
659 **Figure 3A**).

660 GO Cellular Component enrichment localized MV proteomes predominantly to
661 *Extracellular exosome* and *Cytoplasm* compartments (**Supplementary Figure**
662 **3B**). Fraction-specific differences emerged in organellar protein content:
663 mitochondrial proteins showed reduced enrichment in MVs control PLTs, MVs
664 activated PLTs and MVs Plasma relative to MVs MEG-01, while nuclear proteins
665 were uniquely present in MVs MEG-01, which may indicate isolation of
666 intracellular debris containing nuclear fragments from the parent cell line.

667 In summary, these results highlight the central role of conserved hemostatic and
668 communication pathways across all MVs, while also revealing distinct molecular
669 signatures that reflect their diverse cellular origins.

670 ***Exosome Proteomic Characterization Reveals Source-Specific Signatures***
671 ***and Conserved Hemostatic Functions.***

672 EXO proteomes displayed population-specific signatures alongside a conserved
673 core of 375 proteins (**Figure 7A**). Hierarchical clustering via heatmap
674 visualization demonstrated robust segregation of EXOs samples by cellular
675 origin. Venn diagram analysis identified 100 proteins unique to EXOs Activated
676 PLTs, 225 to EXOs Plasma and 736 to EXOs MEG-01. These patterns reflect
677 both conserved vesicle biogenesis machinery and source-dependent cargo
678 selection characteristic of the endosomal pathway.

679 BioPlanet enrichment analysis confirmed that EXOs exhibited proteomic
680 enrichment for hemostatic and immune pathways, although functional activity
681 was not directly assessed. A strong representation of platelet activation
682 programs, coagulation cascades, cell signaling modules, cell cycle regulation,
683 and apoptotic responses was obtained (**Figure 7B**). GO Biological Process
684 enrichment corroborated these hemostatic signatures, proteolytic regulation, and
685 general cellular processes (**Figure 7C**).

686 Reactome analysis reinforced immune and platelet-specific functions, featuring
687 enriched categories including *Hemostasis*, *Platelet activation, signaling and*
688 *aggregation*, *Response to elevated platelet cytosolic Ca²⁺*, *Platelet degranulation*,
689 *Neutrophil degranulation* and *Complement cascade*, consistent with platelet-
690 origin EV biology (**Supplementary Figure 4A**).

691 Subcellular localization analysis revealed a defining characteristic of EXOs:
692 proteins localized predominantly to *Extracellular exosome* and *Blood*
693 *microparticle* compartments, with markedly reduced mitochondrial and
694 nucleoplasmic content compared to PLPs and MVs MEG-01 (**Supplementary**
695 **Figure 4B**). This compositional refinement reflects the selective ESCRT-
696 dependent sorting mechanisms that distinguish EXOs biogenesis through MVBs

697 from the direct membrane budding processes generating MVs and the
698 differentiation pathway producing PLPs.

699 ***Differential Pathway Analysis Reveals Striking Functional Convergence***
700 ***Between EXOs Plasma and EXOs MEG-01.***

701 To identify molecular networks and regulatory mechanisms distinguishing native
702 platelets and their EVs from MEG-01-derived counterparts, differential proteomic
703 analysis was performed using Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA). Native platelets
704 and EVs from platelets and plasma were normalized to their respective MEG-01-
705 derived fractions (PLPs, MVs MEG-01 and EXOs MEG-01), allowing direct
706 assessment of functional similarity. In the resulting heatmaps, orange indicates
707 pathways or upstream regulators more highly activated in MEG-01 fractions, blue
708 indicates reduced activation, and white represents minimal differential activation,
709 signifying functional convergence between populations (**Figure 7D-E**).

710 Native platelets showed pronounced downregulation of biosynthetic pathways,
711 including mRNA maturation (*Processing of Capped intron-containing Pre-*
712 *mRNA*), ribosome biogenesis (*Major pathway of rRNA processing in the*
713 *nucleolus and cytosol*), translational process (*Eukaryotic translation initiation,*
714 *Eukaryotic translation elongation, Mitochondrial translation, Nonsense-Mediated*
715 *Decay and SRP-dependent cotranslational protein targeting to membrane*),
716 alongside with mitochondrial bioenergetics (*Oxidative Phosphorylation*).
717 Conversely, platelets exhibited increased activation of multiple signaling
718 networks (*Netrin Signaling, EPH-Ephrin signaling, Docosahexaenoic Acid (DHA)*
719 *Signaling, Serotonin Receptor Signaling, SNARE Signaling Pathway and eNOS*
720 *Signaling*) and *Phagosome Formation* compared to PLPs (**Figure 7D**).

721 Platelets-derived MVs displayed a nearly identical functional pattern, with
722 downregulation of biosynthetic and bioenergetic pathways and upregulation of
723 the some signaling pathways (*EPH-Ephrin signaling, Docosahexaenoic Acid*
724 *(DHA) Signaling, Serotonin Receptor Signaling, SNARE Signaling Pathway and*
725 *eNOS Signaling*) and *Phagosome Formation* (**Figure 7D**). MVs Plasma exhibited
726 the same downregulation profile but with attenuated z-score intensities, while

727 maintaining only *SNARE Signaling Pathway*. Interestingly, MVs Plasma uniquely
728 displayed *Communication between innate and Adaptive immune Cells*, a
729 function absent in platelet-derived MVs and MVs MEG-01 (**Figure 7D**).

730 In striking contrast, EXOs Plasma showed minimal differential pathway activation
731 compared to EXOs MEG-01, evidenced by predominantly white coloring
732 throughout the heatmap (**Figure 7D**). This remarkable convergence suggests
733 that EXOs Plasma are significantly enriched in megakaryocyte-derived vesicles.
734 Platelet-derived EXOs, however, retained distinct downregulation of biosynthetic
735 pathways: mRNA maturation, ribosome biogenesis and translational regulation,
736 differentiating them from both EXOs MEG-01 and EXOs Plasma (**Figure 7D**).

737 Upstream regulator analysis with IPA revealed contrasting transcriptional
738 programs between native platelets and MEG-01-derived PLPs (**Figure 7E**).
739 Proliferation-associated transcription factors: MYC, RB1 and TEAD1 (a direct
740 activator of MYC in the YAP/TAZ-TEAD pathway)[35], were predicted to be more
741 highly activated in PLPs. In contrast, GATA1, the master regulator of terminal
742 megakaryocyte differentiation, showed elevated activation in native platelets.
743 These findings indicate that despite VPA treatment, MEG-01 cells maintain
744 proliferative transcriptional programs and fail to achieve complete terminal
745 megakaryocytic differentiation, which would be characterized by GATA1
746 dominance and suppression of proliferative drivers like MYC.

747 Additional upstream regulators distinguishing native platelets from MEG-01-
748 derived fractions included receptor-mediated signaling pathways (BCR complex,
749 CD40, INSR, and LH) and pharmacological modulators (1,2-dithiole-3-thione,
750 TYA-018, mono-(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate, and metribolone) (**Figure 7E**). In
751 contrast, native platelets displayed activation of mTOR pathway components,
752 RICTOR (mTORC2), LARP1 (translational regulator downstream of mTORC1),
753 and also mTOR inhibitors sirolimus/Rapamycin and torin 1 are suggested to be
754 upregulated. In addition, FMR1, an RNA-binding protein regulating mRNA
755 splicing, stability, and localized translation is upregulated in native platelets.
756 FMR1's function parallels the selective mRNA trafficking and compartmentalized
757 translation in neurons[36], a similar process that occurs during proplatelet

758 formation in mature megakaryocytes, suggesting native platelets retain
759 sophisticated post-transcriptional control machinery diminished in MEG-01-
760 derived PLPs.

761 Importantly, EXOs Plasma showed minimal upstream regulator differences from
762 EXOs MEG-01, reinforcing their functional convergence observed in pathway
763 analysis (**Figure 7E**). This remarkable similarity contrasts sharply with the distinct
764 proteomic identities maintained by native platelets and platelet-derived EVs
765 relative to MEG-01-derived vesicles. Consistent with previous reports by
766 Flaumenhaft *et al.*[36], our proteomic analysis confirms that EXOs MEG-01
767 exhibit an expression profile characteristic of megakaryocyte-derived EVs.
768 Specifically, these EXOs express CD41 and CD42b but lack the activation marker
769 CD62P, while retaining full-length filamin A (**Supplementary Figure 4C**). This
770 profile distinguishes them from platelet-derived EXOs, which display CD62P and
771 cleaved filamin A.

772 Our findings indicate that EXOs MEG-01 exhibit greater similarity to
773 megakaryocyte-lineage vesicles, thereby supporting their potential utility as
774 surrogate models in experimental studies.

775 **Discussion**

776 This study provides a comprehensive proteomic assessment of MEG-01-derived
777 EVs as surrogate models for selected aspects of platelet EV biology. Through
778 integrative analysis combining morphological characterization, quantitative
779 proteomics, and pathway enrichment, we show that VPA-treated MEG-01 cells
780 generate PLPs, MVs, and EXOs that reproduce several structural and functional
781 features of platelet-derived vesicles, while differences remain in terms of
782 activation state and maturation.

783 Our findings indicate that VPA-induced PLPs exhibit an activated platelet
784 phenotype with elevated CD62P expression, degranulated morphology and
785 "empty" cytoplasmic appearance characteristic of post-secretory platelets.
786 Despite these genotypic and phenotypic similarities, two major challenges
787 prevent complete substitution of native platelets in experimental settings. First,

788 the yield of PLPs obtained *in vitro* remains far below physiological platelet
789 concentrations found in blood, though this limitation could potentially be
790 addressed through bioreactor systems that enhance MEG-01 differentiation and
791 facilitate PLP release and isolation. Second, PLPs predominantly resemble
792 activated platelets with empty cytoplasm post-degranulation, suggesting that
793 PLPs undergo constitutive activation during their generation, leading to
794 premature release of granular contents. This activation-like state limits their utility
795 for studying quiescent platelet biology or early activation events but positions
796 them as valuable models for investigating activated platelet functions relevant to
797 thrombosis and cancer-associated platelet activation.

798 Optimization of PLP purification protocols represents an immediate opportunity
799 to enhance model fidelity by minimizing cellular debris contamination. Our current
800 differential centrifugation protocol effectively separates PLPs from parent cells
801 but co-purifies nuclear fragments and cellular debris, as evidenced by TEM and
802 the persistence of nucleoplasmic proteins in proteomic analysis. Several
803 alternative purification strategies may be evaluated; however, each method
804 presents inherent compromises between PLP yield, sample purity, processing
805 complexity and scalability for experimental applications.

806 First, density gradient ultracentrifugation using discontinuous iodixanol gradients
807 (40-60% gradients) could exploit density differences between intact PLPs
808 (specific gravity ~1.03-1.04 g/mL, similar to native platelets) and cellular debris to
809 achieve superior separation[37]. Second, immunoaffinity purification leveraging
810 positive selection for CD41/CD61-expressing particles through magnetic bead or
811 affinity column separation could provide highly specific PLP isolation while
812 excluding nucleated cells and debris[38]. Comparative proteomic validation of
813 these methods using nucleoplasmic marker quantification, such as histones or
814 nuclear pore proteins, would establish standardized protocols for research-grade
815 PLP production.

816 Beyond purification optimization, improving terminal differentiation could
817 generate PLPs with more physiologically authentic transcriptional profiles. Our
818 data demonstrate that despite VPA-induced morphological maturation, MEG-01
819 cells fail to achieve GATA1-dominant, MYC-suppressed transcription
820 characteristic of terminal megakaryopoiesis. Amplifying GATA1 function

821 represents the most direct approach. While combinatorial treatment with VPA and
822 thrombopoietin receptor agonists, such as romiplostim or eltrombopag, could
823 synergistically activate GATA1-dependent transcription through JAK2/STAT5
824 pathways, genetic strategies offer more precise control[39,40]. Our previous work
825 demonstrated that SCL/TAL1-driven transcriptional networks strongly promote
826 megakaryocytic specification from human embryonic stem cells (hESCs), where
827 TAL1 cooperates with GATA1, LMO2, and related cofactors to reinforce lineage
828 commitment[14]. Building on this concept, Moreau *et al.* developed a
829 megakaryocytic differentiation protocol from human induced pluripotent stem
830 cells (hiPSCs) using lentiviral transduction of three key transcription factors, FLI1,
831 TAL1, and GATA1, which act synergistically to govern megakaryocytic
832 maturation[41]. Following these insights, we utilized the GATA1–FLI1–TAL1
833 lentiviral system to recapitulate macrothrombocytopenia in an hiPSC model of
834 Bernard-Soulier Syndrome Type C. This approach successfully recapitulated the
835 macrothrombocytopenia phenotype *in vitro*, which we subsequently restored
836 through GP9-based gene therapy[42]. Collectively, these forward programming
837 strategies enable highly efficient megakaryocyte differentiation in hiPSCs.

838 Suppressing c-MYC activity represents a complementary regulatory mechanism
839 during megakaryopoiesis. Bourquin *et al.* demonstrated that in acute
840 megakaryoblastic leukemia (AMKL) patients, altered GATA1 function leads to a
841 failure to repress proliferation-associated genes such as c-MYC, contributing to
842 disease pathology[43]. Takayama *et al.* (2010) further showed, using a
843 doxycycline-inducible system, that transient activation of c-MYC is essential for
844 megakaryocyte differentiation from hiPSCs, whereas sustained c-MYC
845 expression beyond the megakaryocyte progenitor stage impairs maturation and
846 reduces platelet release[44]. Pharmacologically, c-MYC inhibition offer practical
847 approaches without requiring genetic manipulation. Small molecule c-MYC
848 inhibitors including 10058-F4 and OMO-103 disrupt MYC-MAX
849 heterodimerization[45], while BET bromodomain inhibitors, such as I-BET-762,
850 block MYC transcriptional activity through chromatin remodeling[46]. These
851 findings highlight the possibility of precise temporal control of c-MYC suppression
852 during the critical phase of megakaryocyte maturation, shifting the differentiation
853 balance toward terminal maturation driven by GATA1 dominance.

854 Beyond VPA, alternative HDAC inhibitors may offer improved terminal
855 differentiation. We and other groups have described that the effectiveness of
856 HDAC inhibitors in promoting megakaryopoiesis and thrombopoiesis varies
857 considerably across cellular models[14] Comparative studies evaluating these
858 compounds, individually or in combination, would establish optimized
859 differentiation protocols yielding PLPs with native-like transcriptional profiles
860 characterized by elevated GATA1, suppressed MYC, and enhanced functional
861 capacity. However, not all HDAC inhibitors are effective for promoting
862 megakaryopoiesis and thrombopoiesis, as their impact varies depending on the
863 specific HDAC target and cellular context. Our upstream regulator analysis
864 identified TYA-018, a selective HDAC6 inhibitor[47] suggesting that HDAC6
865 activity represents a conserved regulatory node distinguishing native platelets
866 from MEG-01-derived populations. Importantly, in humans, HDAC6-selective
867 inhibition preserves nuclear HDAC1/2/3 activity while inducing hyperacetylation
868 of cortactin (CTTN), a central regulator of the actin cytoskeleton, which disrupts
869 actin organization and leads to decreased proplatelet formation[48]

870 The biological relevance and functional capacity of MEG-01-derived PLPs for
871 cancer research applications was recently demonstrated by our laboratory in a
872 companion study. Ceron-Hernandez *et al.* engineered MEG-01 cells to express
873 GFP-tagged oncogenic KRAS^{G12D} and showed that differentiated PLPs carrying
874 this mutation could transfer functional KRAS^{G12D} protein and mRNA to H1975
875 non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) cells, resulting in enhanced tumor cell
876 proliferation, invasion and resistance to tyrosine kinase inhibitors[49]. This
877 transfer confirmed that PLPs can serve as vehicles for horizontal oncogene
878 transfer, recapitulating the tumor-platelet interactions observed *in vivo* where
879 tumor-educated platelets (TEPs) contribute to metastasis and therapy resistance.

880 The complexity of EV preparations arises from their inherent heterogeneity, which
881 is further influenced by the specific isolation methods employed. Differential
882 centrifugation, although widely used and compliant with MISEV2023 operational
883 guidelines, is known to co-isolate non-vesicular components such as cellular
884 debris, protein aggregates, and lipoproteins.

885

886 EV preparations are intrinsically heterogeneous, with each vesicle containing
887 varying concentrations and combinations of molecules as revealed by the
888 multimodal size distribution for both the MEG-01-derived EXOs and MVs of our
889 NTA. This size-based segregation is a critical feature that highlights the inherent
890 biological heterogeneity of these preparations and aligns with the current
891 scientific consensus[50]. Recent sophisticated multi-omics analyses confirm that
892 physical properties like size and density are primary determinants of an EV's
893 molecular identity and functional capabilities. Specifically, physically distinct
894 subpopulations possess fundamentally different protein, lipid, and RNA
895 payloads[51]. Furthermore, this molecular divergence translates directly into
896 specialized biological activities[52]. Nevertheless, EV heterogeneity is currently
897 one of the major challenges that has to be addressed by the EV field. The most
898 recent research aims to accurately characterize the physical and molecular
899 properties of EVs at the individual vesicle level. This allows us to know what each
900 vesicle contains and how it differs from the others. However, there is no single
901 perfect technology for this task. For example, AF4-based size fractionation
902 enables the enrichment of distinct EV subpopulations, including large EVs (90–
903 120 nm), small EVs (60–80 nm), and exomers (<50 nm). Biochemical analyses
904 reveal marked compositional and functional differences among these subsets,
905 underscoring the need for advanced high-resolution fractionation platforms and
906 improved methods to map molecular localization across particle sizes[53]. High-
907 resolution fractionation of EVs remains a significant technical challenge, primarily
908 limiting the separation of distinct functional subpopulations based on subtle size
909 differences.[50].

910 Another critical challenge in this area is the isolation method. Differential
911 centrifugation, although widely used and compliant with MISEV2023
912 guidelines[20], is known to co-isolate non-vesicular components such as protein
913 aggregates, lipoproteins, and cellular debris. These impurities may influence
914 proteomic profiles and obscure functional interpretation. While measures such as
915 exosome-depleted FBS, sequential filtration, and marker-based validation reduce
916 contamination, complete removal of non-vesicular material is technically difficult.
917 Future studies should incorporate additional purification strategies, such as
918 density gradient ultracentrifugation or immunoaffinity capture, and consider

919 complementary non-vesicular reference fractions to further improve sample purity
920 and refine functional interpretation.

921 The comparative proteomic analysis of MVs MEG-01 and those of platelet origin
922 reveals a substantial overlap, with nearly the entire platelet MV proteome
923 represented in the MVs MEG-01 dataset. Both vesicle types share biogenic
924 mechanisms, characterized by cytoskeleton-dependent budding regulated by
925 calcium signaling and the Rho/ROCK pathway, resulting in marked structural and
926 functional homogeneity[54]. Functionally, MVs MEG-01 are enriched in canonical
927 platelet pathways, including PI3K subunit p85 in actin organization and cell
928 migration, Platelet activation, signaling, and aggregation, and Hemostasis,
929 underscoring their preservation of hemostatic, metabolic, and immunomodulatory
930 features typical of platelet-derived vesicles[55]. Minor variations, such as
931 upregulation of MYC and translation pathways, are attributable to the
932 megakaryocytic origin of MEG-01 cells, but do not result in significant proteomic
933 differences between the two MV types.

934 These findings establish the MEG-01 cell line as a robust and versatile *in vitro*
935 model for studying platelet MV biogenesis and molecular mechanisms, as well as
936 facilitating genetic manipulation of MV populations. Moreover, this model serves
937 as an ideal platform for developing therapeutic strategies based on MVs with
938 defined hemostatic and immunomodulatory properties.

939 The most striking finding of this study was the remarkable proteomic convergence
940 between EXOs Plasma and EXOs MEG-01, evidenced by minimal differential
941 pathway activation and near-identical upstream regulator profiles in IPA analysis.
942 This unexpected similarity intersects with an ongoing debate regarding the
943 cellular origins of circulating CD41⁺/CD42b⁺ EVs. While traditionally attributed to
944 activated platelets, accumulating evidence suggests that megakaryocytes
945 directly contribute a substantial fraction through constitutive release mechanisms.
946 Flaumenhaft et al. demonstrated that circulating CD41⁺/CD42b⁺ microparticles in
947 healthy humans are predominantly CD62P⁻ and express full-length filamin A,
948 molecular signatures characteristic of megakaryocyte-derived rather than
949 platelet-derived microparticles. This distinction is critical: CD62P (P-selectin)
950 marks activation-induced vesiculation from mature platelets, whereas its absence
951 indicates megakaryocytic origin through constitutive, non-activated release[56].

952 Holcar et al. reinforced this complexity, reporting that plasma EVs positive for
953 CD41/CD42b but negative for CD62P likely originate from megakaryocytes,
954 though relative contributions remain debated given the vast numerical disparity
955 between circulating platelets ($150\text{-}410\times 10^9/\text{L}$) and bone marrow megakaryocytes
956 ($\sim 0.05\%$ of nucleated cells)[57]. Nevertheless, each megakaryocyte produces
957 2,000-10,000 platelets and directly releases submicron vesicles, establishing the
958 megakaryocytic lineage as one of the most prolific EV-producing cellular systems.

959 However, this convergence should not be interpreted as definitive enrichment of
960 megakaryocyte-derived vesicles in plasma exosomes. Plasma EVs are highly
961 heterogeneous and originate from multiple cell types, and the fraction analyzed
962 here may be influenced by isolation protocol and starting material. Other blood
963 cell-derived EVs may share core hemostatic or cytoskeletal proteins, and our
964 analysis focused on proteomic and pathway-level comparisons rather than
965 comprehensive surface marker profiling beyond CD41/CD42/CD63, which would
966 require additional targeted approaches to fully resolve cellular origin. Therefore,
967 the observed similarity suggests a substantial contribution of
968 megakaryocyte/platelet lineage EVs to the plasma exosome proteome under
969 these conditions, but additional studies using broader marker panels and
970 orthogonal approaches will be required to confirm lineage-specific enrichment.
971 The proteomic convergence we observed likely reflects that MEG-01 cells, which
972 constitutively produce CD41⁺/CD42b⁺/CD62P⁻ exosomes, share molecular
973 features with megakaryocyte-derived EV populations present in plasma. This
974 similarity suggests that MEG-01-derived exosomes may serve as useful models
975 for subsets of plasma EVs enriched in megakaryocyte/platelet lineage markers,
976 while acknowledging that plasma EVs are heterogeneous and include
977 contributions from multiple cell types.

978 Beyond biomarker applications, the convergence between MEG-01 derivatives
979 and natural counterparts (platelets, platelet-derived EV and plasma EVs) has
980 immediate therapeutic implications. This work opens multiple avenues for
981 mechanistic investigation of platelets: dissecting molecular determinants of
982 tumor-platelet adhesion using engineered PLPs with mutated or deleted
983 integrins; modeling TEPs biology by exposing PLPs to tumor-conditioned
984 medium and profiling transcriptomic/proteomic changes and studying platelet-

985 mediated protection of circulating tumor cells from immune surveillance.
986 Moreover, platelets and platelet-derived EVs are being explored as natural
987 nanocarriers for targeted drug delivery in cancer therapy, leveraging their tumor-
988 homing properties, extended circulation half-life and immune compatibility[58,59].
989 EXOs MEG-01 could accelerate this translational pipeline by providing
990 standardized, genetically modifiable starting material for drug loading
991 optimization, surface engineering (peptide display, antibody conjugation) and
992 preclinical efficacy testing in orthotopic tumor models.

993 Future work should integrate optimized purification methods with enhanced
994 differentiation protocols to generate second-generation MEG-01 derivatives that
995 more faithfully recapitulate native platelet biology. Strategies could include
996 conditions favoring either activated or quiescent phenotypes, depending on
997 experimental needs. For activated states, options include combining VPA with
998 platelet agonists such as thrombin or GPVI ligands to mimic physiological
999 activation cascades. For quiescent states, measures such as calcium depletion
1000 during isolation, addition of prostaglandin E1 (PGE1), and optimized buffer
1001 composition could help prevent premature activation. Further differentiation
1002 refinements may involve thrombopoietin receptor agonists, GATA1 upregulation,
1003 or transient MYC suppression to promote terminal maturation without activation.
1004 In parallel, single-cell RNA sequencing of differentiating MEG-01 populations
1005 could identify transcriptional trajectories and bottlenecks, guiding targeted
1006 interventions. Single-vesicle proteomics using advanced mass spectrometry or
1007 proximity ligation assays could resolve heterogeneity within EV populations and
1008 identify subsets with maximal physiological fidelity. Finally, *in vivo* biodistribution
1009 studies comparing MEG-01 EVs versus native platelet EVs in tumor-bearing mice
1010 would validate therapeutic potential and inform clinical translation strategies.

1011

1012 **Conclusions**

1013 MEG-01-derived EVs provide important advantages as experimental models,
1014 offering a standardized and scalable source with defined proteomic properties
1015 that facilitate reproducibility and controlled manipulation. These features make
1016 them particularly useful for studies requiring consistent EV preparations and

1017 genetic engineering. Our comprehensive proteomic analysis demonstrates
1018 strong convergence with megakaryocyte- and platelet-derived EVs in
1019 hemostasis-related and cytoskeletal pathways, supporting their use as surrogate
1020 models for selected aspects of platelet EV biology. However, they remain
1021 surrogates rather than full equivalents of native platelets. Limitations include
1022 incomplete terminal megakaryocytic differentiation, persistence of proliferative
1023 transcriptional programs, and a predominance of activation-like phenotypes
1024 rather than quiescent states, as well as the transformed genotype of MEG-01
1025 cells, which may influence vesicle composition. These conclusions are based on
1026 proteomic and pathway enrichment analyses, not on direct functional assays.
1027 Future optimization of purification and differentiation protocols could further
1028 enhance physiological relevance, positioning MEG-01 derivatives as practical
1029 platforms for biomarker discovery, mechanistic research, and exploratory
1030 therapeutic applications in oncology and regenerative medicine.

1031

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1036 G.M.-N., J.C.-H., C.M.L., and A.P.-M.; writing original draft: J.M.S.-M, C.T. and
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1058

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1060 Raw mass spectrometry data from this experiment have been deposited in the
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1070 **Conflicts of Interest:**

1071 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

1072

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1296

1297 **Figure legends:**

1298 **Figure 1:** VPA-induced Megakaryocytic differentiation of MEG-01 GFP+ cells.
1299 **(A)** Optical microscopy images of VPA-treated MEG-01 GFP+ cells captured on
1300 days 2, 4, 7, 10, and 14 at 20x (upper row) and 40x (lower row) magnification,
1301 illustrating morphological changes during differentiation. **(B)** Transmission
1302 electron microscopy images of VPA-treated MEG-01 GFP+ cells, highlighting
1303 ultrastructure changes during megakaryocytic differentiation. Arrows indicate key
1304 features. (B1) Presence of polylobulated nuclei in megakaryocytes; (B2) thick
1305 pseudopodia extending from the plasma membrane, contributing to proplatelet
1306 formation; (B3) release of proplatelets or nascent platelets via cytoplasmic
1307 membrane evaginations and pseudopodia. **(C)** Flow cytometry analysis of
1308 megakaryocytic surface markers CD41-PE and CD42a-APC in VPA-treated vs.
1309 control MEG-01 GFP+ cells, assessed every 4 days. Data represent the mean \pm
1310 SD of quintuplicate experiments analyzed using Holm-Šídák's multiple unpaired
1311 t-test: ns $p > 0.05$, * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$, **** $p \leq 0.0001$ vs. Control. **(D)**
1312 Representative ImageStream images of VPA-treated MEG-01 GFP+ cells,
1313 showing the localization and expression GFP (cytoplasmic/nuclear, green),
1314 CD41-PE (plasma membrane, yellow), Hoechst (nuclear DNA, purple), and
1315 CD42a-APC (plasma membrane, red). The merged panel, excluding brightfield,
1316 integrates all channels, highlighting cellular organization during differentiation.

1317

1318 **Figure 2:** VPA-Driven Differentiation of MEG-01 GFP+ Cells Generates PLPs
1319 Resembling Activated Platelets. **(A)** Transmission electron microscopy images
1320 depicting ultrastructural features of platelets and PLPs across physiological and
1321 experimental conditions: (A1) Control platelets (Control PLTs), maintained in a
1322 resting state with PGE1, showing intact cytoplasmic granules and a discoid
1323 morphology; (A2) Activated platelets (Activated PLTs), stimulated with an
1324 activation cocktail (Collagen, ADP, and CaCl_2), showing degranulation,
1325 membranous bodies, and cytoplasmic content release; (A3) Thrombus-
1326 associated platelets, exhibiting isolated and Activated PLTs at the periphery and
1327 compact mass of Activated PLTs in the thrombus center; (A4) PLPs from VPA-
1328 treated MEG-01 GFP+ cells, a heterogenous population resembling Activated
1329 PLTs (A2) but including MEG-01 fragments and necrotic debris. **(B)** Flow
1330 cytometry analysis of megakaryocytic differentiation markers (CD41-PE and
1331 CD42a-APC) in PLPs isolated by differential centrifugation from VPA-treated (2
1332 mM) MEG-01 GFP+ cell supernatant. Differentiation analysis was assessed
1333 every four days. Data represent the mean \pm SD ($n=5$) analyzed by Holm-Šídák's
1334 multiple unpaired t-test: ns $p > 0.05$, * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$, **** $p \leq 0.0001$
1335 vs. Control. **(C)** Flow cytometry analysis of platelet activation marker CD62P-
1336 Pacific Blue (P-selectin) in Control PLTs, Activated PLTs, and PLPs. Both, Mean
1337 Fluorescence intensity (MFI) and percentage are shown. Data represent mean \pm
1338 SD ($n=3$) analyzed by one-way ANOVA: ns $p > 0.05$, * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, ***
1339 $p \leq 0.001$, **** $p \leq 0.0001$ vs. Control. **(D)** Representative ImageStream images of

1340 Control PLTs, Activated PLTs, and PLPs derived from VPA-treated MEG-01
1341 GFP+ cells. Channels indicate localization and expression levels of GFP
1342 (cytoplasmic, green), CD41-PE (plasma membrane, yellow), CD62P-Pacific Blue
1343 (plasma membrane, purple), and CD42a-APC (plasma membrane, red). The
1344 merged panel, excluding brightfield, integrates all channels highlighting
1345 phenotypic similarities and differences between platelets and PLPs.

1346

1347 **Figure 3:** Phenotypic Characterization of Microvesicles (MVs) from VPA-treated
1348 MEG-01 GFP+ cells, Platelets and Plasma. **(A-D)** Size distributions (nm) of MVs
1349 derived from VPA-treated MEG-01 cells **(A)**, Control (resting state) PLTs **(B)**,
1350 Plasma **(C)**, and Activated PLTs **(D)**, measured by nanoparticle tracking analysis
1351 (NTA). Distributions represent the mean \pm SD of five 10-second video analyses
1352 (n=5). Representative transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images
1353 accompany each distribution, illustrating MVs size and morphology. **(E)** MVs
1354 concentrations for each sample type (particles/mL of blood in the case of MVs of
1355 Plasma, Control & Activated PLTs, and particles/mL of media in the case of MVs
1356 MEG-01), presented as mean \pm SD from triplicate measurements (n=3). Data
1357 represent mean \pm SD (n=3) analyzed by one-way ANOVA: ns p>0.05, * p \leq 0.05,
1358 ** p \leq 0.01, *** p \leq 0.001, **** p \leq 0.0001 vs. MVs Control PLTs. **(F)** Zeta potential
1359 (mV) of MVs from each sample type, measured in triplicates and presented as
1360 mean \pm SD (n=3). **(G)** Representative ImageStream images of MVs from VPA-
1361 treated MEG-01 GFP+ cells, Control PLTs, Activated PLTs, and Plasma.
1362 Channels indicate localization and expression levels of GFP (cytoplasmic, GFP),
1363 CD41-PE (plasma membrane, yellow), 7AAD (DNA, pink), Annexin V-Pacific
1364 Blue (phosphatidylserine on plasma membrane, purple), and CD42a-APC
1365 (plasma membrane, red). The merged panel, excluding brightfield, integrates all
1366 channels highlighting phenotypic profiles for each sample type and confirming the
1367 absence of apoptotic bodies.

1368

1369 **Figure 4:** Phenotypic Characterization of Exosomes (EXOs) population from
1370 VPA-treated MEG-01 GFP+ cells. **(A-D)** Size distributions (nm) of EXOs from
1371 VPA-treated MEG-01 cells **(A)**, Control or resting PLTs **(B)**, Plasma **(C)**, and
1372 Activated PLTs **(D)**, measured by NTA. Distributions represent the average
1373 analysis of five 10-second videos, presented as mean \pm SD (n=5).
1374 Representative TEM images accompany each panel, illustrating EXO
1375 morphology and size (50-250 nm). **(E)** EXO concentrations for each sample
1376 (particles/mL of blood in the case of EXOs Plasma, EXOs Control and EXOs
1377 Activated PLTs, and particles/mL of media in the case of EXOs MEG-01),
1378 presented as mean \pm SD from triplicates (n=3). Data represent mean \pm SD (n=3)
1379 analyzed by one-way ANOVA: ns p>0.05, * p \leq 0.05, ** p \leq 0.01, *** p \leq 0.001, ****
1380 p \leq 0.0001 vs. EXOs Control PLTs. **(F)** Zeta potential (mV) of the different EXO
1381 samples, measured in triplicate and presented as mean \pm SD (n=3). **(G)**
1382 Representative ImageStream images of EXOs generated by VPA-treated MEG-
1383 01 GFP+ cells, control platelets, activated platelets, and plasma. Channels show

1384 localization and expression levels of GFP (cytoplasmic, green), CD41-PE
1385 (plasma membrane, yellow), CD63-PECy7 (plasma membrane, pink), and
1386 CD42a-APC (plasma membrane, red). The merged panel, excluding the
1387 brightfield channel, combines all fluorescence channels to highlight the
1388 phenotypic profiles of each sample type.
1389

1390 **Figure 5.** Proteomic and Functional Characterization of MEG-01 Cells and their
1391 Extracellular products. (A) Heatmap illustrating differentially expressed protein
1392 profiles across MEG-01 cells (green), platelet-like particles (PLPs) (blue),
1393 microvesicles (MVs) (yellow), and exosomes (EXOs) (brown). The accompanying
1394 Venn diagram highlights shared and unique proteins subsets detected within
1395 each group. (B) BioPlanet pathways enrichment analysis, and (C) Gene Ontology
1396 (GO) Biological Process analysis, each presenting the top 10 most significantly
1397 enriched biological processes or pathways ranked by adjusted p-value. The
1398 diameter of each bubble denotes the number of proteins associated with a given
1399 pathway or process, while bubble color intensity reflects the enrichment score for
1400 each individual sample type: MEG-01 cells (green), PLPs (blue), MVs (yellow),
1401 and EXOs (brown). (D) Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and t-distributed
1402 Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE) maps segregating MEG-01 cells, PLPs,
1403 MVs, and EXOs and their natural human platelet-derived counterparts: Platelets
1404 (PLTs), as well as associated MVs and EXOs from Control or Activated PLTs.
1405 Each sample replicate is mapped individually, maintaining group-specific color
1406 scheme. MEG-01 derived products are grouped within a green area, platelets in
1407 purple, MVs in light blue, and EXOs in orange, illustrating distinct clustering and
1408 phenotypic boundaries between these populations.
1409

1410 **Figure 6.** Comparative Proteomic and Functional Analysis of Human Platelets,
1411 MEG-01 Cells, and their derived populations. (A) Heatmap illustrating differential
1412 protein expression across Control Platelets (green), Activated Platelets (blue),
1413 PLPs (yellow), and MEG-01 cells (brown). The accompanying Venn diagram
1414 shows shared and unique protein subsets, revealing both overlapping and distinct
1415 molecular signatures. (B) BioPlanet pathway enrichment analysis showing the
1416 top 10 most significantly enriched biological pathways, ranked by adjusted p-
1417 value, for each sample type. Bubble size indicates the number of proteins
1418 mapped to each pathway, and color intensity reflects the enrichment score. (C)
1419 Gene Ontology (GO) Biological Process enrichment analysis presenting the top
1420 10 most enriched biological processes for each group. Bubble diameter
1421 represents the number of associated proteins, and color intensity indicates the
1422 enrichment score per group. (D) Heatmap and Venn diagram depicting
1423 differential protein expressions in MVs from Control Platelets (green), Activated
1424 Platelets (blue), Plasma (yellow), and MEG-01 cells (brown). (E) BioPlanet
1425 pathway enrichment analysis of MVs from Control Platelets, Activated Platelets,
1426 Plasma, and MEG-01 cells, showing the top 10 most enriched pathways. Bubble
1427 size reflects the number of proteins, and color intensity indicates the enrichment

1428 score. (F) GO Biological Process enrichment analysis of MVs, presenting the top
1429 10 most enriched processes. Bubble diameter corresponds to protein count, and
1430 color intensity reflects the enrichment score for each group.

1431

1432 **Figure 7.** Comparative Functional and Upstream Regulator Analysis of Human
1433 Platelets, Plasma, MEG-01 Cells, and their extracellular vesicles. (A) Heatmap
1434 illustrating differential protein expression profiles of key biological functions
1435 across EXOs purified from Control Platelets (green), Activated Platelets (blue),
1436 Plasma (yellow), and MEG-01-cells (brown). The accompanying Venn diagram
1437 highlights shared and unique protein subsets, revealing overlapping and distinct
1438 molecular signatures. (B) BioPlanet pathway enrichment analysis showing the
1439 top 10 most significantly enriched biological pathways, ranked by adjusted p-
1440 value, for EXOs Control PLTs, EXOs Activated PLTs, EXOs Plasma and EXOs
1441 MEG-01. Bubble size indicates the number of proteins mapped to each pathway,
1442 and color intensity reflects the enrichment score. (C) Gene Ontology (GO)
1443 Biological Process enrichment analysis presenting the top 10 most enriched
1444 biological processes for each sample type. Bubble diameter represents the
1445 number of associated proteins, and color intensity indicates the enrichment score
1446 for EXOs Control Platelet, EXOs Activated Platelet, EXOs Plasma, and EXOs
1447 MEG-01. (D) Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA) comparing key biological
1448 functions inferred from relative protein expression in natural products (Platelets,
1449 MVs and EXOs) and their MEG-01-derived counterparts (PLPs, MVs MEG-01
1450 and EXOs MEG-01). This panel highlights the 10 top most differentially up or
1451 down-regulated functions distinguishing native and engineered populations. (E)
1452 IPA-based prediction of the top most significantly relevant upstream regulatory
1453 mediators driving proteomic differences between natural and MEG-01-derived
1454 populations.

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1457 **Supplementary Figures:**

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1459 **Supplementary Figure S1.** Proteomic and Functional Characterization of MEG-
1460 01 Cells and their extracellular products. (A) Reactome pathways enrichment
1461 analysis displaying the top 10 most significantly enriched biological processes or
1462 pathways ranked by adjusted p-value. (B) Gene Ontology (GO) cellular
1463 component analysis of the six most relevant components: extracellular exosome,
1464 nucleoplasm, cytoplasm, mitochondria, membrane and blood particle. For both
1465 panels, the diameter of each bubble represents the number of proteins
1466 associated with a given pathway or cellular component, while the color intensity
1467 of the bubbles reflects the enrichment score specific to each sample: MEG-01
1468 cells (green), PLPs (blue), MVs (yellow), and EXOs (brown).

1469

1470 **Supplementary Figure S2.** Proteomic and Functional Analysis of Human
1471 Platelets (Control and Activated), MEG-01 Cells and PLPs. (A) Reactome
1472 pathway enrichment analysis showing the top 10 most significantly enriched
1473 biological processes or pathways, ranked by adjusted p-value. (B) Gene
1474 Ontology (GO) Cellular Component analysis highlighting the six most enriched
1475 components: extracellular exosome, nucleoplasm, cytoplasm, mitochondria,
1476 membrane, and blood particle. In both cases, bubble diameter represents the
1477 number of proteins per component, with color intensity indicating the enrichment
1478 score for each sample type (MEG-01 cells: brown; PLPs: yellow; Control PLTs:
1479 green; Activated PLTs: blue).

1480

1481 **Supplementary Figure S3.** Proteomic and Functional Analysis of MVs Obtained
1482 from Human Platelets (Control and Activated), Plasma, and MEG-01 Cells.
1483 (A) Reactome pathway enrichment analysis presenting the top 10 most
1484 significantly enriched biological processes or pathways, ranked by adjusted p-
1485 value, for each sample group. (B) Gene Ontology (GO) Cellular Component
1486 analysis, highlighting the six most enriched components, extracellular exosome,
1487 nucleoplasm, cytoplasm, mitochondria, membrane, and blood particle. In both
1488 panels, bubble size corresponds to the number of proteins mapped to each
1489 component or pathway, and color intensity reflects the enrichment score for each
1490 group: MVs Control PLTs (green), MVs Activated PLTs (blue), MVs Plasma
1491 (yellow), and MVs MEG-01 (brown).

1492

1493 **Supplementary Figure S4.** Proteomic and Functional Analysis of exosomes
1494 (EXOs) Purified from Human Platelets (Control and Activated), Plasma and MEG-
1495 01 Cells. (A) Reactome pathway enrichment analysis displaying the top 10 most
1496 significantly overrepresented biological pathways or processes for each exosome
1497 sample group, ranked by adjusted p-value. (B) Gene Ontology (GO) Cellular
1498 Component analysis highlighting the six principal components: extracellular
1499 exosome, nucleoplasm, cytoplasm, mitochondria, membrane, and blood particle.
1500 For both panels, bubble diameter indicates the quantity of proteins assigned to

1501 each pathway or component, while color intensity signifies the enrichment score
1502 for each group: EXOs Control PLTs (green), EXOs Activated PLTs (blue), EXOs
1503 Plasma (yellow), and EXOs MEG-01 (brown). (C) Log2-transformed expression
1504 levels of CD41 (green), CD42b (blue), CD62P (yellow), and Filamin A (red) were
1505 measured in EXOs isolated from control platelets (EXOs Control PLTs), activated
1506 platelets (EXOs Activated PLTs), plasma (EXOs Plasma), and MEG-01 cells
1507 (EXOs MEG-01). Boxplots in each panel represent protein abundance for the
1508 respective group.

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